

**THE FIRST NOTICE OF THE DOSITHEANS BY
ABU 'L-FATHĪ BIN ABI 'L-ḤASAN AD-DINFĪ**

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1. This article is the second in a series on the textual and exegetical difficulties of the history of the Samaritans by Abu 'l-FathĪ bin Abi 'l-Ḥasan ad-DinfĪ (A.F.).¹⁾ The first ar-

²⁹⁾ As has been the case with D.H. Sanders' publication of the work of T.B. Goell on Nemrud Dağ: D.H. Sanders (ed.), *Nemrud Daği: the hierotheseion of Antiochos I. of Commagene. Results of the American excavations directed by Theresa B. Goell*, I-II (1996).

³⁰⁾ Albeit more limited in scope and subject (an architectural and urban level) also P. Richardson, *City and sanctuary. Religion and architecture in the Roman Near East* (2002) is useful here, aiming at a comparison in cultural character between Palmyra, Petra, Gerasa, Caesarea and Jerusalem.

³¹⁾ Quotes from K. Butcher, *Roman Syria and the Near East* (2003) 333-334 and M. Sommer, *Roms orientalische Steppengrenze. Palmyra-Edessa-Dura-Europos-Hatra. Eine Kulturgeschichte von Pompeius bis Diocletian* (2005) 405.

¹⁾ This is not the place to go into questions of the sources and composition of the book as a whole. What was written by Vilmar in his introduc-

ticle (2005) was a study of the transmission of the Samaritan histories corresponding to the books of Joshua and Judges, with two sections on the manuscripts of this book and sets of representative samples of various categories of textual difficulties, with solutions to the samples.²⁾ The articles are

tion is still not superseded (see 6. **Bibliography**, first title). The author wrote his history of the Samaritans in 756 A. H. = 1355 A. D. His name Abu 'l-Faḥḥ bin Abi 'l-Ḥasan as-Sāmīri ad-Dīnfi is complete as an official name, but otherwise is not complete, in that he does not give his personal name. This would be because the self-naming by the author near the start of his foreword is a formal act, launching the book as a publication. We have no document naming him in relation to his kin. Like many historians writing in Arabic, A.F. used old sources that are otherwise unknown. One of his sources on the Dositheans was also known to Origen at second hand, though Origen misunderstood it.

²⁾ There are two closely related lines of transmission of the narrative corresponding to Joshua and Judges, both in Arabic. One is the core of the book now known as the Arabic Book of Joshua. I say the core, because material is prefixed to this and added to this before and after in many mss., the extent varying from ms. to ms. In addition, all mss. have a long and tedious passage interpolated. The passage is from the period of Byzantine rule in Syria-Palestine, and is concerned with supposed battles of Joshua against Iranians of various types, including Persians. It is this interpolation that has misled superficial readers into thinking the core text to be a late fiction. The translator tells us he translated from an Aramaic text which he thinks to have been translated from Hebrew. In the Leiden ms. this statement has suffered from homoioteleuton and seems to say the Arabic was translated from Hebrew. There are numerous mss. with the original reading. (See my article "The Transmission etc". and Jamgotchian). The second line of transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges is a superior and uninterpolated text of what is now the core of the Arabic Book of Joshua, used by Abu 'l-Faḥḥ. He knows of the readings of the inferior line of transmission of the Arabic Book of Joshua and warns against them. The elaborate fantasies of a Hebrew text of Joshua extant in the mediaeval period that are sometimes put forward can be dismissed. None was known to the translator from Aramaic to Arabic in about 1050. Even the Aramaic was an abridgment. No Hebrew text was known to A.F. in 1355, and by then even the Aramaic abridgment was lost. The Hebrew text circulated from early 1908 onwards is translated from an important Arabic history written in 1875 by the well-known scholar Khaḍr bin Ishāq or Fīnāās ban Yēṣāāq פִּינְאָס בֶּן יֵצְחָק. (See my article on all this. For general usage a good simplified transcription would be Finaas ben Yeṣaaq). In the Joshua section Khaḍr faithfully copies the Arabic Book of Joshua, a very well-known book. The first edition of the Hebrew was a slightly simplified verse translation from the Arabic of Khaḍr. The second and third editions of the Hebrew have massive slabs from the Masoretic Text added. The Hebrew book is accordingly written in two different kinds of Hebrew. No deception was intended by the authors of the Hebrew book, who only wanted to present simplified information to outsiders unable to handle the original sources. It would have been inconceivable to them that anyone could not recognise such a well-known work as the History by Khaḍr. (There are mss. everywhere). The Arabic work by Khaḍr is cited frequently in the present article, but with an understanding of what it is and is not.

Some mistakes were introduced into my article "The Transmission etc." by the editors. I give here the most important correction. On p. 13, example (g), on Abu 'l-Faḥḥ 156:6, the first two instances of final ٢ are to be changed to final ٣. I take this opportunity to give my later considered opinion on the intended reading here. After looking at the styles of writing final ٢ and the other final letters of similar shape, it seems that a final flourish on the top left corner in some styles could be mistaken for a cursive final ٢ without dots, so that final ٢ could be interpreted as ٣ which would then be copied with dots. Otherwise, the final ٣ can be explained as misunderstanding of the two dots of a medial ٢ just before the last letter. Both factors could have worked at once. It seems simplest to regard the Arabic letters as originating in an unthinking transcription of two consecutive Aramaic words both meaning "caim", mēṭob and tūtāb, read as one word מְטוֹב תּוֹטֵב and transcribed مَوْتَوْتَوْتَب with this unintelligible combination of letters being copied later as مَوْتَوْتَوْتَب and then مَوْتَوْتَوْتَب. (The medial form of the Persian letter [p] پ represents a short upward line without dots. This specific scribal error producing a medial ٢ does occur. I have seen it). The two Aramaic words with the same meaning are both in the mss. of the Targum at Gn XXXI:47. From the distribution of the readings in the mss. of the Targum, the second word could be later. (The word תּוֹטֵב is not recorded in Tal's *Dictionary of Samaritan Aramaic*. Mss. E and C of the Targum as well as the old Aramaic glossary seem not to have been col-

lated as Vorstudien for a future critical edition, whether by an individual or by a committee. Whether such an edition is brought out soon or next century does not matter for the present purpose. The immediate purpose of this second article in the series is to give an accurate Arabic text and accurate translation of the first notice of the Dositheans, with enough notes to justify the text and translation, to make the author's intention clear, and to make his data useable.³⁾ It is hoped that studies of other sections of text, including the second and third notices of the Dositheans, will follow. A study of the overall plan followed by Abu 'l-Faḥḥ when incorporating the disparate sources and their disparate chronologies is also planned.

A few words on the need for a new critical edition are appropriate here. The edition by Eduardus Vilmar in 1865 is impressive. There are several main reasons for seeing the need for its replacement. They can be reduced to the premature end of the author's academic activity, the technical limitations of working just before the use of photography, the limited range of textual families accessible in Europe at the time, and the incomplete knowledge of relevant realia at the time. Vilmar sometimes prints what is not in any manuscript, without any notice to the reader. The number of such instances is not great, but most of them are in critically important places. In a few places the reader is told, but the information is incomplete and sometimes misleading. It can be conjectured that he intended to give full textual notes in his planned second volume, never published. The published book has two title-pages on facing pages. On the right is the page I have cited in the bibliography. On the left is the title-page of an edition intended to be two or three volumes. "Abulfathi Annales Samaritani. Quos Arabice Edidit cum Prolegomenis Latine Vertit et Commentario Illustravit Eduardus Vilmar". It is not known what happened to the author. In some places that are critically important all the old manuscripts available in Europe at the time go back to an ancestral exemplar that was smudged or faded in places. The scribes have sometimes indicated the uncertainty, but the transcripts used for the edition have not recorded this. Vilmar often prints an inferior reading unique to C or D without any note in the apparatus. He was sometimes mistaken over the details of the text of C. It is often hard to tell the difference between diacritical dots and lines and mere decorative flourishes in this ms., and repeated re-reading of the original or a photograph after becoming very familiar

lated for the dictionary, even though they were used for the apparatus of the edition of the Targum edited by Tal. The published liturgy seems not to have been fully collated either. An article or note will follow). If the two words Mēṭob Lībi were an inherited fixed phrase, and the word mēṭob had become archaic, then the insertion of the alternative word tūtāb as a gloss in a written text could easily occur. The vocalisation [mētāb] will be treated elsewhere.

³⁾ The spelling used here is according to the consensus of the mss. If there is divergence, SBD have been followed. The spelling is standard for the period and reflects the pronunciation pretty well. The rules of pronunciation for modern Syrian-Palestinian Arabic will serve as a guide for the present purpose. There is nothing specifically Samaritan in the Arabic. The text printed in this study never departs from the mss. Even where a reading is marked with daggers, it is never without some ms. evidence. In such instances, either the remains of a word partly lost have been restored, or I have followed what was the reading of the Arabic ms. slightly expanded by Khaḍr and also used for the Hebrew translation. The Arabic mss. used for these two works and for copying ms. A are not currently accessible. They seem to have been 19th c. transcripts of very old and accurate originals.

with the scribe's habits is needed. The scribe says this was his first ever manuscript, and it shows. We now have access to the fragments in St. Petersburg, which in some places preserve the original reading against all the complete manuscripts and all the incomplete manuscripts. Thanks for a systematic start on the use of this material are owed to my colleague Prof. Haroutun Jamgotchian in his book of 2003. Much more remains to be done. Besides this, we now have modern transcripts of old material in Nablus, including the careful work of the High Priest Ya'qûb bin Hârûn or Yââqob bin Aârron יעקב בן אהרון in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century. (Jamgotchian is bringing out an edition of his Hebrew translation). Finally, we now understand better what the author's sources were getting at, from a better knowledge of historical circumstances. There are places where A.F. says he hesitates to quote more from his source because he does not understand all of it.⁴)

As is well known, Abu 'l-Fath has three notices of the Dositheans. Although the sources for these notices are disparate, he does not try to reconcile them. There is an apparent discrepancy in the dating of Dositheus which has occasioned much speculation, but it can be resolved. In the first notice, Dositheus is dated after the death of the person called Simon the Just in the Rabbinic chronology and before Alexander the Macedonian, that is, late in the period of Persian rule. In the second piece, Dositheus is put after two accounts of the time of the Emperor Decius (249-251 A.D.) and possibly after the time of the illustrious Germanus

⁴) In the translation of Abu 'l-Fath by Paul Stenhouse it is asserted on p. xxviii of the introduction that the translation is based on a critical edition by the same person. (The Kitâb al-Tarîkh [sic] of Abu 'l-Fath translated into English with Notes by Paul Stenhouse M. S. C., Ph.D., Mandelbaum Trust, University of Sydney, 1985). Stenhouse's words there do not say that this edition has been published, only that the translation has been published. The same words say a microfiche is obtainable from the publisher of the translation, but no title or date is mentioned. My inquiries about this have not been answered. On the evidence of what is and is not in Stenhouse's own words, along with the non-existence of an ISBN, and the absence of this microfiche from any Australian library or any European library on the usual indexing systems, what he calls an edition is not a publication. I obviously don't know anything of a photocopy made for private use. I have seen Stenhouse's doctoral thesis, and verified that it does match the published translation. The Arabic text used for the translation is unsatisfactory. It is not accurate by any normal academic standards. Here are some (not all) of the categories of error. It is enough to compare the translation and its notes. Often a wrong guess by Vilmar is followed against all the manuscripts and without showing any awareness that there is a difficulty. See 82:1-2. In some places the clear intention of the scribes has been misrepresented or not noticed. See specially 83:14-15. The readings attributed to S*CD at 82:15 are false. The right decision has been made, but the evidence is much stronger than what is stated, so what ought to be a certainty has been reduced to a probability. In some places Vilmar's erroneous collations have been copied or a reading has been used where Vilmar is misleading by silence; see for instance 82:12, 83:3, 83:11-12; 156:6. In some places a reading limited to ms. C alone and explicable as a misuse of diacritical dots or an error has been followed without comment. See for instance 82:9-10. The references and allusions to the wording of the Torah by Abu 'l-Fath are consistently not seen, with an effect on the interpretation of the manuscript evidence. See 82:6 and 82:9. Arabic vocabulary, morphology, and syntax are often not understood, with a consequent effect on the interpretation of the manuscript evidence. See 83:11 and 83:9. Hebrew and Aramaic terms are often not recognised, with a consequent effect on the interpretation of the manuscript evidence. See 82:1-2. The halachah, whether Jewish or Samaritan, is often not understood, with an effect on the interpretation of the manuscript evidence. See 82:9 and 83:1. This makes fourteen mistakes in twenty-eight lines, all serious enough to show up even through the intermediary of the published translation. Some other instances of all this are given in my article in note 6, where I point out that Stenhouse's identification of the manuscripts themselves is not entirely accurate.

Bishop of Neapolis (early fourth century),⁵) but before the account of Simon Magus, Philo Iudaeus, and Jesus. Yet A.F. has an account of Jesus in the right setting at 107:7-14. It is obvious that A.F. has not tried to integrate his sources here. Instead, he has marked the long second account of Dositheus with the word فصل as a new major section. Speculation as to whether there was more than one person by the name of Dositheus is therefore pointless. The same argument that would duplicate Dositheus would put Simon Magus, Philo Iudaeus, and Jesus after the middle of the second century A.D. or otherwise after the Council of Nicaea! What seems to have happened is that two High Priests in two separate lists, both called Iqbon עקבון have somehow been linked by him, perhaps arbitrarily so as to avoid having to try to guess the solution. Resolving the question of the dating depends on identifying the bounds of the main blocks of information taken over by A.F. This question will be treated exhaustively in a future article. Dositheanism seems to be earlier than the Hellenistic conquest, though it must have had some other name. The Christian tradition sets Dositheus in the first century A.D., in part associating him with John the Baptist. A.F. seems to accept the same date. The third account, the sects derived from the Dositheans, is in its right place just after the accounts of Simon Magus, Philo Iudaeus, and Jesus. In the time of Abu 'l-Fath, both the Dositheans as a separate denomination, and their opponents as a separate denomination, had vanished, being replaced by a new orthodoxy mutually acceptable to both parties. For instance, the doctrine of resurrection was re-phrased. The ecumenical process took centuries. When Al-Kitâb al-Kâfi was written, in 433 A.H. (1042), it had been purposefully under way for about forty years, apparently connected with a decision by all parties to re-cast their Aramaic literature into Arabic. (Their Greek literature had apparently already been re-cast into Hebrew.) While it is true to say, then, that Abu 'l-Fath knows of the Dositheans only what he has found in books, it is just as true that it is only from books that he knows the theology of their opponents. Not knowing enough to integrate the content or chronologies of his sources, he has kept them separate.

The first account is a mildly hostile but informative brief note from 82:3 to 83:15 (see Arabic text below) on the practices of the movement, with a mention of the later leadership of the son of the High Priest. The second notice, at 151:11-157:9, seems to be composite. There is a long embroidered account of Dositheus himself, the son of the High Priest. Then there is an account of the death of Dositheus; the formation of a small but highly placed group of followers just afterwards; the murder of לִי בֶן פִּינְאָס Lîbi ban Fînâās, the nephew of the High Priest, the Dosithean Protomartyr; and a description of the practices of the sect. The third notice, at 159:12-164:11, is a listing of sub-sects said to derive from the Dositheans. Not all these movements have any obvious connection with the Dositheans. At least one is Gnostic or Naassene. It might well be that here we have the literary model for the ascription by Irenaeus of all heresies regardless of type to the first impetus of Simon the Samaritan. Actually, there are indications of a common source behind one of the books used by A.F. and one of the sources of Irenaeus in his opening section. The Samaritan

⁵) Germanos is mentioned with gratitude in the Samaritan liturgy to this day.

tradition knows of Simon only what could have been learnt from Christian sources, and knows him as a Jew, not a Samaritan. The Christian tradition only knows of Dositheus what could have been learnt from Samaritan sources. It seems Simon has the same place for Irenaeus as Dositheus has for the source of the third notice in Abu '1-Fath. It follows that Simon and Dositheus are probably the same historical figure and the common source of the later legendary embroidering.

The separate data having been clarified one by one, the next question is whether there is any pattern to the listing. There are at least five summaries from a halachic midrash, at 82:8 on the wild category of permitted animals; at 82:9-10 on graves; at 82:12-14 on the status of Mt. Gerizim during the time of the Fānūta, that is, in the present era; at 83:1-3 on leprosy of houses; and again on leprosy of houses at 83:3-5. There are two other possibilities at 82:6, on the uncleanness of springs; and at 82:6-8, on the counting of seven days. Some of these passages can be seen as arguments intended to prove the validity of a particular middah, that is, a rule of method of halachic midrash. Judging by what is quoted on leprosy of houses, the illustrations, or perhaps better the introductory illustration, would have been chosen for their simplicity and effectiveness, not whether they could ever be applied at all. On the other hand some items do concern daily life. The status of Mt. Gerizim would have been vitally important. The nearest parallel is not any Rabbinic text, but rather the Book of Deductions or Decisions (גזרות) of the Sadducees. (The defective spelling is used deliberately, since the meaning of the title of the book is not certain yet. For some representative extracts from this book and a characterisation of it, see my *L'Antiquité des Racines du Karaïsme*, part 4). The way the passage on the Mountain is worded shows it was near the opening. "They asserted that the scripture they had, by the Children of the Apostle, had in it [or: "could show"] that God might be served in the Land of Zawīlah till he might be served on Mt. Gerizim" (82:12-13). There must therefore have been subject order to some extent in the original Dosithean book, with the central tenets and their proof coming first. Beyond this it is precarious to say anything about the order, but the following main sections seem to have been before the author of the summary: the tenets defining the movement with a statement of the source of their authority; eschatology; principles of exegesis of the Torah; halachot of specific subjects; biography of Dositheus and his successors. The hostile narrative opening here could be a re-writing of an opening setting out the purpose of the work of Dositheus. The explanation of the symbolic name of Dositheus fits a handbook for both internal use and proselytising. From the words at the end, this book seems not to have been the same as the one written by Dositheus, though obviously relying on it. The name of it was probably The Book of the Children of the Apostle בני השליה. The extract has some structure. The narrative start and finish are well placed. So are the words in the middle. "They counted the fifty days from the day after the Passover Day as the Jews do, making all their offensiveness public". This takes attention away from the disparateness of the listing before and after. The practices most visible to outsiders are clustered together from 82:11 to 83:1. These taken together show why they would have had to have separate synagogues and separate Priests. The rest look as if they have been listed as found. This line of examination will become more effective once the lists in

the second and third notices are clarified. After that, the next step is to list the principles of theology, exegesis, and halachah preached publicly by the movement. It should then be feasible to work out why Dositheus was needed in the mid first century A. D.

2. Arabic Text

(٣٤٨٢) وفي ذلك الوقت انفصل من (٤) السامرة جماعة وعملوا لهم مذهبا بمفردهم وسميوا الدستان لاجل (٥) ابطالهم اعياد الحق وجميع ما نقلوا من ابايهم واجدادهم وخالفوا (٦) السامرة في اشيا كثيرة منها ان كل منع ما يوجد فيه شرص ميت يطمونه واذا حاضت المراه لا يحسبوا لها الا من غد ذلك النهار شبه الاعياد (٧) من الغروب الي الغروب وحرموا اكل البيض الا الذي يوجد عند (٨) ذبح الطاير وكذلك طموا جنس الحيات بعد موتها وطموا اصل (٩) المقابر وقالوا كل من وقع ظله على المقابر يتنجس سبعة ايام وحرموا (١٠) قول **برוך آلهينو لآلهم** وقول **يهوه** كما (١٢) نقلوها الطايفه وكانوا يقولوها **آلهيم** وادعوا ان السفر الذي (١٣) معهم لاولاد الرسول فيه ان الله يخدم في ارض زويله الى حين يخدم (١٤) في هرجزيم ويطلوا حساب الزيج وكانوا يعملوا بالعدد كل شهر (١٥) ثلاثين يوما لا غير وابطلوا الاعياد والضحية وابطلوا فريضة الصيام (١٦) والنصيب وكانوا يعدوا الخمسين من غد الفسح مثل اليهود وابطلوا (١٧) كل كريبتهم † كانوا † يدخلوا الى البيت الناظر ينظروا ما فيه ولا يتكلموا (٢) واذا خرجوا الى برا يكونوا طاهرين والبيت ناظر قياسا على البيت (٣) الوضع واذا كان بيت طاهر متصل بالبيت الطمي واراوا يعرفوا ان كان (٤) طاهرا او طميا يعقدوا انسانا مقابله ينظر فان حط عليه طاهر طاهر (٥) طهروه وان حط عليه طاهر طمي طموه وكانوا يوم السبت لا (٦) يستحلون ياكلون ولا يشربون في انيا تحاس ولا جزاز ولا ما يدخل (٧) عليه الطمي ويظهر الا في انيا فخار اذا طمي لم يمكن تطهيره وما كانوا (٨) يطعموا بهيمه ولا يسقوها في يوم السبت الا يهيو لها قدامها ما (٩) تحتاج اليه من يوم الجمعة وكانوا يخالفون السامرة في اشيا كثيرة من (١٠) سوتى اعتقادات واحكام ولذلك افتردوا منهم وجعلوا لهم كتابيس (١١) بذاتهم وكاهنه بذاتهم وكان ابن الرئيس الكبير امامهم وذلك ان (١٢) الجماعة شهدوا عليه شهاده محققه انهم وجدوه مع خايطه فاحرموه وابعده (١٣) وكان اسمه زرعه فلما ايس من الجماعة مال الى الدستان (١٤) فقبلوه وجعلوه امامهم فعمل كتابا بايحا † الحرم احرم † فيه كل الايمه وابدع فيه فان (١٥) لم يكن في زمانه اعلم منه ولذلك اسمه † زرعت †

3. Translation

[82:3] At that time a group left [4] the Samaritans, and set up for themselves a denomination on their own. They were called the Dositheans. This [move] was a result of [5] their discontinuing of the rightful Festivals as well as everything handed down from their parents and forebears. They differed from [6] the Samaritans in many matters. For instance, any "spring of water" (Lv XI:36) in which a dead šēreš (שרץ) (same verse) was present (verses 29, 32, 36) was considered unclean by them. When [7] a woman menstruated (see Lv XV:19) they did not start her counting (of seven days; same verse) till the following day, in the manner of the Festivals, [8] "from sunset till sunset" (see Lv XXIII:32). They forbade the eating of eggs except for what was found on [9] slaughtering the fowl. As well as this they declared unclean the wild category of permitted animals (Dt XIV:5) after their [natural] death (Lv XI:39-40). They declared graves [10] unclean in themselves. They said that anyone that overshadows a grave is made unclean for seven days (see Nu XIX:14 and 16). They forbade [11] the saying

of “Blessed is our God forever”. They forbade [the pronunciation] Shēma [for the Tetragrammaton] as [12] in the nation’s tradition, and would say it as Ē’luwwem [God]. They asserted that the scripture [13] they had, by the Children of the Apostle [Dositheus], had in it [or: “could show”] that God might be served in the Land of Zawīlah (زويله; Gn II:11 = the Balātah Meadow) till he might be served [14] on Mt. Gerizim [the location of the occulted Garden]. They abolished the calculation of the almanac and would set the length of every month [15] at thirty days, never otherwise. They discontinued the Festivals and the Passover sacrifice. They discontinued the commandment of the fasting [16] and Priestly share (نصيب = Hebrew תרומה *tērūma*). They counted the “fifty days” (till Pentecost; see Lv XXIII:15) from the day after the Passover Day as the [Pharisaic] Jews do, making [83:1] † all † their offensiveness public. They † would † go into a house that was nāṭir (sequestered for seven days; Aramaic נטר *nāṭer*; see Lv XIV:38). They would inspect it (see verse 39) without saying anything, [2] and on coming outside, they would be clean and the house would be nāṭir (see verse 36 and verse 40). This was on the same principle (see verse 36) as with a house [3] that was visibly leprous for the first time (واضح *waḏiḥ*; see verses 34-39). If there was a clean house, joining onto the unclean house, and they wanted to know whether it was [4] clean or unclean, they would seat someone in front to watch; and if a clean bird lit on it [5] they would declare it clean; and if an unclean bird lit on it they would declare it unclean. On the Sabbath, they did not [6] allow eating or drinking from vessels made out of glass or anything that [7] can be cleansed after acquiring uncleanness; but instead vessels made out of pottery, which is uncleanable once it has become unclean (see Lv VI:21). They used not to [8] feed or water an animal on the Sabbath; but would set out for it in front of it [9] what it needed on the Friday. They differed in many matters from the Samaritans, [10] in both beliefs and practices. For that reason they separated themselves from them and set up their own [11] synagogues and their own Priests (Kāhinah). The son of the Great Rabbī [High Priest] became their High Priest (Imām). This was because [12] the community had testified against him with verified testimony that they had found him with a loose woman, and had then disqualified him [from officiating as a Priest] and removed him [from office]. [13] His name was Zā’rāā (زرעה = זרעה). When he despaired of the community he went over to the Dositheans, [14] who accepted him and made him their High Priest (Imām). He then composed a book in which he revealed the things sacred. He said in it that any High Priests (A’immah) other than himself were illegitimate. He was entirely original in it. This was because [15] no-one in his time was more learned than him: consequently his name † Zār’rēēt †.

4. Manuscripts and Textforms

For full details of the mss. collated, see my “The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges”. The sigla are as fixed by Vilmar for mss. ABCD(E)F, and by Jamgotchian for St. Petersburg fragments GHIJKLMN. I have added the sigla J₁L₁L₂L₃M₁N₁P₁SYH₁H₂. Here very briefly is the explanation of the rest of the sigla. Ms. J₁ = part 1 of ms. Sam. Octavo 5 in Jerusalem (1908). L₁ = British Library ms. Oriental 2080 (1863). L₂ = BL Oriental 1447. (First half by Musallam bin Marjān, between about 1695 and 1705. Second half written in 1868). L₃ = BL ms. Oriental 12257 (be-

tween 1900 and 1905). M₁ = John Rylands Manchester ms. Sam 260 (near the end of the 19th century). N₁ = Jewish Theological Seminary, New York, ms. Adler 1356 (between 1865 and 1880). P₁ = ms. Firkovitch Samaritan VI:19 in the Russian National Library in St. Petersburg, written in 1863. S = ms. Sassoon 36 (about 1500, but with leaves from a suppletor working in 1699). Y = Yale University Library ms. 663 in Landberg’s listing (1868). It is to be remembered that the modern mss. are transcripts, or transcripts of transcripts, of old exemplars. H₁ and H₂ are the Hebrew translation by the High Priest Ya’qūb bin Hārūn (the siglum H₂ being provisional pending publication of a study by Jamgotchian, who might designate it otherwise). Ms. H₁ is ms. Samaritan 256 of the Rylands Library at Manchester University. Ms. H₂ is in St Petersburg. It will be described separately.

Here is the division of the mss. into groups. Group 1(a). Some of the St. Petersburg fragments are of the same family as 1(b) but from a branch unaffected by the corruptions in the text of Group 1(b) and unaffected by the physical damage in an old ancestral exemplar. (The fragments have been classified by Jamgotchian. They need not be treated here as they do not include this section of text). Group 1(b) are old mss. with a single narrow tradition and all copied in part (directly or indirectly) from an original that was faded or washed out in spots. S with B (copied from S but sometimes correcting it) CDFL₂ (first part). Ms. S is very good. C is good where accurately written but most of its unique readings are simply mistakes. D is often secondary or wrong, but better than C. Where B differs from S its reading is often the result of good purposeful collation and is often the best. Group 1(c). Mss. L₂L₃Y. These are inferior mss. of the type of 1(b). Group 2. These are J₁L₁M₁N₁P₁. These are all later than the members of Groups 1(a) and 1(b), and some of their readings are certainly secondary (which does not mean corrupt). In my assessment, it would be wrong to class all the distinctive readings of this group as secondary. Aside from this, in places where CD are corrupt and SB are not very good, they can have a better text. The fact that they are all relatively late can be looked at the other way, by pointing out that Group 1 is not very big, 1(b) has a narrow base, and 1(a) is smaller and fragmentary: so to some extent the accident of what was chosen for copying at one period could be giving a misleading picture. More on this in another article in this series. Group 3. One member, A. This ms. is unique in its type and uniquely important. In some respects it resembles Group 2, but it largely goes its own way. Where it differs in substance from the other mss. it often has genuine information from an alternative tradition not otherwise known. There are instances of this in the list of Dosithean practices in the third notice, as will be shown in another article. There are numerous correct glosses and numerous instances of re-wording greatly improving the clarity. Group 4. One member. This is the very good ms. used by Khaḏr bin Ishāq (Fīnāās) in his History. (See note 2). In the section treated in this article, he sometimes expands the wording of the original, often coming up with a clearer statement in better style. He almost fully understood the text (but not quite always). Sometimes he adds correct glosses. Otherwise he just reproduces the original. It is not at all hard to see what he had before him in his ms. This same ms. must have been collated by the Hebrew translator, as its distinctive superior readings often appear in the translation in difficult places. The relationship between the groups is probably connected

to the question of the two editions of the history. Nearly all the mss. end at the time of the Islamic conquest with a highly prominent encomium of Muḥammad. Mss. P₁ and A and St. Petersburg fragment H go further; ms. C and St. Petersburg fragment K go further still. One purpose of the majority text is as a book of self-definition written for the benefit of the official status of the Samaritans as a recognised Ṭā'ifāh. But the author seems to have extended the book to his own time for internal use by the community. This question is to be treated later.

The collations given here are complete in all difficult places, or where the content varies, or where re-wording is substantial, or where ms. A has a useful gloss.

5. Annotations and Commentary

82:3-4. Ms. D (followed by Vilmar) and L₂L₃Y have انفصل من جماعة السامرة فرقه which is an inferior reading, from a time when the Dositheans and the rest had reached a consensus and amalgamated, no-one quite remembered what the question had been, and Dositheans were some faction mentioned in books, not a good half of the population.

82:4-5. The syntax and order of phrases show that this was why they had to be a separate community, not why they were called Dositheans.

82:6. As he often does, Vilmar has followed a unique and inferior reading of ms. C, presumably because this was the oldest known to him. The omission of كثيره does not make sense. On the other hand, D has the obviously corrupt reading اشيانهم or اتيانهم leaving only BA available to him with the correct reading. Vilmar suffered from the difficulty that it is only after a book has been edited and printed that you can fully see the qualities of the mss. Ms. L₂ followed by L₃Y has followed D with اشياتهم (and L₃Y then omit منها) The same omission by M₁N₁* is harder to explain.

82:6. Vilmar has omitted the word ميت against all the mss. The two Arabic words منبع ما “a spring of water” are obviously a translation of the third and fourth words מעין מים in Leviticus XI:36 (that is, the second word ما does not mean “what”, but “water”). Note that the MT omits the third word of the verse. The word שרץ šēreṣ is taken from the same verse. For a list of the nine kinds of land-dwelling šēreṣ that are unclean see Lv XI:29-30. Contrary to common misconception, they are not all reptiles. The citation of part of the Samaritan halachic argument on this subject in the Palestinian Talmud is very condensed. (‘Avodah Zarah 5:4 = 44d bottom). First we are told that the discussion applies to pools. We are told that the Samaritans do not immerse themselves in “drawn water” (that is, water of a pool not filled up at some time by an uninterrupted flow of springwater or rainwater or water from a river or melting ice). Then we are told the Samaritans do not agree with the Rabbinic requirement of a minimum volume and do not find this in the verse. Then the verse is quoted, but according to the Jewish version (in the extant mss. anyway). The following is a reconstruction of the argument. First, it is argued that the plain meaning of the words of the verse is that what is true of a spring must be true of a pool. I think the next step in the argument is that the verse says both a spring and a pool continually fed by upwelling or outwelling water are always clean, dead šēreṣ or not. It is then argued that it logically follows that the water of either must always be effective for immersion, regardless of volume, since it says the water of both can always negate the presence of the šēreṣ.

This is only partly the known Samaritan opinion. There is agreement on the question of volume, though obviously the person or utensil being cleansed has to be fully covered by water. There is, however, disagreement in the other respect. The known Samaritan opinion, which is the same as the Rabbanite and Karaite opinion, is that the flow of a spring can never be unclean, but a pool can become unclean and then clean. At the time of writing this article I don't know what the Samaritan argument is for finding this distinction in the words of the verse. All three parties agree that the person or utensil being cleansed in the spring must obviously not touch the dead šēreṣ. The only qualification by the Samaritans is that if the water of the spring is deep enough to be still at a deep level, then the still water is not effective for immersion till the dead šēreṣ has been taken out and the water at the deep level has been replaced naturally; but this does not affect the cleanness of the flowing water. All Karaites agree (definitely against the Rabbanites!) that the water of both a spring or a pool must be free of pollutants to be effective for immersion. A minority of Karaites add that pollution must be assumed as long as the šēreṣ is present, and that the water has to be allowed to replace itself after the šēreṣ is taken out. The Dosithean opinion cited here by A.F. is that even a spring can be made unclean. They probably argued that since in this verse טמא means “becomes unclean”, then יהיה טהור must mean “becomes clean”, not “is clean”. It would follow that a pool can be made unclean. The word يوجد being present, not past, the meaning can only be that the flow of the spring is unclean while the dead šēreṣ is still in it, and not that it is unclean afterwards. They presumably argued that whereas the water of a spring would replace itself, a pool has to be drained and re-filled. The known Samaritan halachah does in fact maintain that a pool remains unclean even after the šēreṣ is taken out, and has to be drained and re-filled. We have, then, three versions of Samaritan halachah on this matter: the one cited in the Palestinian Talmud, otherwise unknown; the one quoted in all the extant Samaritan sources; and the Dosithean. All agree on the question of the volume of water. The opinion cited in the Talmud seems to be that neither a spring nor a pool ever becomes unclean. The known opinion is that a pool can become unclean, but not a spring. The Dositheans maintained that a spring could become unclean.

Mss. M₁N₁P₁ with A have an expanded text influenced by the known Samaritan halachah, and probably due to a clever but mistaken guess. They have: “Any spring of water in which a šēreṣ is present, and in which a dead šēreṣ had been found”. What the scribes mistakenly thought and meant was that the Dositheans took the known Samaritan halachah in regard to a pool and applied it to the case of a dead šēreṣ in the flow of a spring, that is, that the spring is unclean even after the šēreṣ is taken out. This guess won't work, first, because every spring must have a dead šēreṣ in it at some time, and second, because every spring will change its water and replace it with clean water. It might be due to familiarity with the Karaite sources, which use this double reduction to absurdity to prove that the flow of a spring must be presumed to be clean, and cite the contrary opinion as an opening gambit. The scribes have had difficulty. Ms. A has كل منبع ما يوجد فيه شرص ووجد فيه شرص ميت. M₁N₁ have glossed the first occurrence of شرص with اي نجاسه. P₁ has replaced this word by شرطن which I take to be due to a mistake in the word سرطن which represents the modern Syrian pronunciation of the literary form سرطان meaning a crayfish. Not a

good guess at all. L₃Y have شرط which is meaningless, and probably derived from the word in P₁ or a related ms. N* omits ما يوجد فيه. M₁ omits ما يوجد. M₁N₁ have في instead of فيه. Y adds في after ميت which is inexplicable. There has been cross-collation somewhere. L₃Y have the translation جامع מקוה instead of منبع. This is a wrong guess, from the halachah known to the Scribes.

82:6-8. Modern Rabbinic Judaism agrees with the Dositheans in requiring a count of seven complete periods from sunset to sunset. That means of course with the period up to the sunset of the first period being part of the time of uncleanness. This makes part of a day followed by seven complete days. In this modern Rabbinic Judaism departs from the standard of the Mishnah and Talmud and the intention of Scripture, and follows a folk practice mentioned by the Talmud and rejected by it. According to Maimonides in the relevant section of the Mishneh Torah, the new practice came in immediately after the close of the Talmud, by decree. The Dosithean practice was known to the Tanna'im as a Samaritan practice. See my *Principles of Samaritan Halachah*, p. 202 and p. 204, with the cross-references. On the exact intention of the quote from Lv XXIII:32, see the Kitāb al-Khilāf, lines 200-201, and my notes. The Dositheans would not have over-ridden Scripture in the Rabbanite manner. They probably found what they took to be a Scriptural argument by arguing from the words כימי נדתה “as the days of her niddā” in Lv XII:2.

82:8-9. As is observable in daily life, neither Jews (Rabbanite or Karaite) or Samaritans eat fertilised eggs. A fertilised egg inside a properly slaughtered fowl can be eaten. The rule is that the slaughtering of the chook is the slaughtering of the egg. The case mentioned here is not the norm, but rather the special case that shows the principle, which is that a fertilised egg is alive (for the present purpose) but is obviously outside the required slaughtering, so it can't be eaten. This is the classic short illustration in Rabbinic texts. The Dositheans were rigorous, מהמירים. Their practice has nothing surprising in it. Jews and other Samaritans will obviously eat eggs they know for certain are not fertilised. The Dositheans were presumably not convinced you could be absolutely certain from observation of the signs in the egg, perhaps because what has to be observed is actually the absence of signs.

82:9. From the Torah, there are two categories of permitted animals, those normally domesticated in Syria-Palestine in ancient times and those not. The first category are cattle, sheep, and goats (Deuteronomy XIV:4). The second category are all species of deer, gazelle, antelope, bison, wild sheep, and wild goat. The Torah lists seven species of these in the next verse. Abu 'l-Fath lists these seven kinds at 31:10. The second category are termed in this context היה ayyā [Masoretic היה] in Samaritan and Jewish usage using the hints in the wording of the Torah, and the first category is contrasted in this context by the term בהמה bīmā [Masoretic בהמה]. The Arabic word jins here means category, that is, the category characterised by seven species in Deuteronomy XIV:5 and referred to in halachic discussion as היה. This category is contrasted here to the first category of cattle, sheep, and goats. The reason the word حیات “wild animals” is in the plural is that the reference is to the seven kinds. The reason the plural has an Arabic form is that for A.F. and his community the word had been borrowed into Arabic. The corpse of an animal in the category of cattle, sheep, and goats that has died by itself or been killed but not

as prescribed causes uncleanness by touching or carrying. As well as this, a person that has eaten it becomes unclean. This last type of uncleanness is from having eaten, as distinct from touching. Note well that this last type of uncleanness can only be caused by eating a **permitted** animal. The term for animal here is בהמה which is ambiguous. Does it only mean cattle, sheep, and goats, or does it mean all permitted animals, reindeer and giraffes and water buffaloes and so on? If the meaning is restrictive, then a dead addax or oryx or deer does not cause uncleanness in any way. This is doubly anomalous, since the corpse of an animal not to be eaten does cause uncleanness by touching, and the corpse of a sheep not killed in the prescribed way causes uncleanness by touching. It is even triply anomalous, since the meat of a sheep not killed in the prescribed way causes uncleanness by having been eaten. (It stops having this effect once it has passed from the duodenum to the small intestine, because chemical change has occurred. See Mark VII:19). The practical effect of this decision by the Dositheans is hard to see. The conclusion must then be that this bit of halachah of theirs was meant to be the instance that conclusively proved the validity of one of their accepted principles of halachic argument, which would have been some aspect of the use of analogy from two opposite directions. The way the two terms היה and בהמה are used in the Torah makes it fairly easy in this case. See specially the usage in Dt XIV:4 and Lv XI:39-40. If the principle is valid here where the argument is compelling, then it is valid elsewhere. Compare the note on the item of halachah at 83:3-5, which could equally well be an illustration.

82:9-10. The mechanism of acquiring uncleanness mentioned in the second sentence is what in Rabbinic Hebrew terminology is called אהילה with the corresponding verbs from the same root. The term comes from Numbers XIX:14. It is clear that the following verse, about a person coming into contact with a human corpse or a grave in open country, must include the case of overshadowing ground under which is a corpse, since we are not told otherwise, and in the case of a grave or tomb it is certain there will be no touching of the corpse. I use the term “overshadowing” without talking about shadows, as anyone with a good command of English will know. In the same way, Abu 'l-Fath talks of a person's shadow without talking about partial blockage of sunlight, as anyone with a good command of Arabic will know. This “overshadowing” might mean having the feet on the ground right over where the corpse is, or equally well leaning over where the body is. Obviously a person going inside a tomb will become unclean by being under the same roof as the corpse (verse 14). But what the Dositheans asked was what happened in the case of someone that leant over or stood over a stone coffin (whether buried or not) or a tomb without touching it and without being over the corpse. They came up with what could be called “overshadowing of overshadowing”. If anything inside the tomb or stone coffin is unclean by אהילה without touching the corpse, then the room inside is unclean, so anyone that stands or leans over the tomb or stone coffin without standing or leaning over the corpse must become unclean by אהילה of this אהילה that is, by overshadowing the unclean space. It remains possible that the word ظل “shadow” was chosen because the Dositheans extended the concept of leaning over to being within four cubits. only C; وبقی only C; وقالوا all others. بنجس SB; يطمي all others. The reading of SB is correct. This is not meant to be a quotation. It is the **deduction** that the person is made unclean for seven days.

It is thus certain that Abu 'l-Faṭḥ used the word ظل "shadow" in the second sentence. It is unlikely that he would have used it in the first sentence. How could anyone be overshadowed by a tomb? If inside the tomb, then there is nothing new, since the answer in this case is already known and could not have been a matter for disagreement. The case of walking underneath a suspended stone coffin without exactly being underneath the corpse is remote. Vilmar, working from transcripts, thought this word was there. Here are the details of what is in the mss. Mss. SCD don't always separate words, and they don't always put an alif at the end of a plural verb. This ambiguity of where the alif belongs applies here to every ms. except L₂ which is ambiguous in other respects, as will be seen. Ms. S has ضل which is meaningless. It might or might not have alif at the start of the word. D has ظل which is meaningless. It might or might not have alif. CL₃Y have ظل and might or might not have alif. L₂ has ظل and no alif, but it has no alif at the end of the previous word either, which is unexpected spelling for this ms. Ms. B unambiguously has اصل (origin, identity, separate existence in some contexts) and thus deliberately departs from S, its exemplar. Readings in B disagreeing with S tend to be good. Note, however, that there is no alif at the end of the previous word in B and the words are joined. All mss. of the second group have اصل and so has A. Of these, AP₁ join the word with the previous word; J separates the words (but has no alif at the end of the previous word); M₁N₁ unambiguously have اصل with another separate alif at the end of the previous word, so there no doubt at all that اصل is what is intended; L₁ has اصل unambiguously (but omitting the previous word); the Hebrew translation unambiguously translates اصل. The paraphrastic quotation by Khaḍr bin Ishāq assumes the same reading. In short, there is nothing about overshadowing in the first phrase, and the intended meaning is certainly as I have translated. Khaḍr tells us that the Dositheans treated graves or tombs as unclean in themselves. The meaning is that they treated contact with graves or tombs (on the outside) as equivalent to contact with a corpse. It might seem, on the basis of Numbers XIX:16, that this is required, but the known Samaritan halachah, as well as the Karaite and Rabbanite halachah, put restrictions on the acquisition of uncleanness in this way. For instance, the Kitāb al-Farā'id (ch. CV) limits contact to contact with remains, and this seems to be the assumption of the long commentary on the Torah. If I read the Kitāb al-Farā'id correctly, a stone coffin (jurn) causes seven days' uncleanness by contact, but a structure that is not portable, that is, a tomb, doesn't. On the other hand, Al-Kitāb al-Kāfi, in ch. XIII, knows the concept of ground that is ناطر that is, unclean due to remains or graves, and capable of causing uncleanness by contact, apparently for seven days. It is clear from the context of the argument that the author is not thinking of contact with remains. It is equally clear that he doesn't distinguish between a grave and a tomb. It seems, then, that the Dositheans were in agreement with the author of Al-Kitāb al-Kāfi. Neither is this the only instance of such agreement, surprising as this might be. The author of Al-Kitāb al-Kāfi says expressly that up till his generation it was the general custom to consider a person whose shadow fell on a grave (in the meaning established above) as unclean for seven days, and that this practice had been discontinued just before his book was written, by a decree of the current High Priest. Furthermore, he says that up till his time it had been customary to treat throwing

stones at a marked grave or a tomb as equivalent to direct contact, causing seven days' uncleanness. This is certainly "being extreme in regard to the outside of graves", as Khaḍr puts it. It is therefore justifiable to interpret this notice by Abu 'l-Faṭḥ in the light of what the author of Al-Kitāb al-Kāfi is familiar with. He does not say a word about the shadows of graves, but has lots to say about the uncleanness of graves in themselves.

82:11. SDBL₂L₃Y as printed here; C: يهوه; A: النطق في اسم يهوه; L₁: النطق باسم יהוה; JN₁: יהוה; M₁: النطق اسم الله. As said elsewhere, Jamgōtchian has proven that the original text of this book had Hebrew and Aramaic names and terms written in Arabic letters, so I am inclined to see the Arabic letters in A as original. (The reading in C might be original or might be secondary). All the same, I have not departed from the principle set out originally of printing what is actually in the mss.

82:10-11. Appel's suggestion that the Dositheans did not like the expression "Blessed is our God forever", because by not saying "forever and ever" it could be interpreted as denying resurrection, has merit. [M. Appel, *Quaestiones de Rebus Samaritanorum sub Imperio Romano Peractis*. Breslau 1874]. Certainly the Rabbinic parallels are clear. This is not, however, the only possible explanation. They might not have considered it appropriate in the time of the Fānūtā, which by definition is not permanent. They might have wanted to keep the expression for the coming Time of Favour רחוקה Rūūta which by definition is to be permanent. The essence of Dositheanism is the waiting for the end of the present provisional period and the restoration of the Tabernacle and the full holiness of the Mountain.

82:12 – 14. A.F. 155:1 – 2: "My faith is in thee, Lord, and in Dositheus thy servant, and his sons and daughters". 156:14 – 15: "They said the dead would rise soon, as children of Dositheus the Prophet of God [i.e. the successor of Moses]"; but in ms. A: "They said the dead would soon rise, thanks to Lībi לוי and his party, the children of Dositheus the Prophet of God". The verb used here and translated "served" is not applicable to synagogue worship. It is the verb used for the service of the Tabernacle. (It is the verb used by Christians for the offering of the Mass). There is nothing specifically Dosithean in the doctrine of the Tabernacle being occulted in the present era, the Fānūtā; or in the expectation of its manifestation in the Time of Favour, the רחוקה Rūūta. [The ה is a vowel-letter. The root is רעי with a second infinitive רעותה rē'ūta in the meaning of "willingness" and so on]. What was distinctive was their logical development of the doctrine into the treatment of the Mountain as only potentially holy at the present time. Compare 161:13-14: "He (Sakta) declared Mt. Gerizim profane, the same as any other mountain; and said anyone praying facing Mt. Gerizim might as well pray facing a grave". The logical consequence of this view would be to suspend the three pilgrimages at Passover, Pentecost, and Booths till the coming of the Time of Favour. Compare 162:16-163:1: "He (Sakta) discontinued going up the Noble Mountain"; 161:12: "He (Sakta) started making changes to the Festivals". The Festivals would have been observed, but without the pilgrimage. This is the Jewish reasoning and practice. The meaning must then be that study, worship, and prayer in the Dosithean sacred place on the Balāṭah Meadow will somehow eventually lead to the manifestation of the Tabernacle on the Mountain. (Balāṭah is right next to Old Shechem, across the road). Compare 161:7 – 8: "He (Sakta)

said 'Come over to me and see how the Tabernacle appears'. They made him a tent (مظلة) in which he started teaching. He said 'From this tent we will go up to Mt. Gerizim'. Epiphanius or his source mentions a roofless stone structure like a theatre standing on the Meadow about two Roman miles down from the later Neapolis. The big tent would have been inside this. (Panarion, LXXX:1). The place was probably identified by them with the place of Jacob's vision and thus holy in its own right. There is a tradition setting Luzah on the Meadow recorded by Eusebius, Onomastikon, entry "Louza". This is said to be inside the third milestone from Neapolis, corresponding to the location of the structure reported by Epiphanius as being on the flat ground at about the second milestone. The persistence of such a tradition is seen in the Arabic name of the Meadow مرج البهاء "the Field of the Glory". For the origin of the name, see the Targums on Gn XXVIII:16-17. Presumably the Dositheans pictured Jacob on the Meadow seeing the angels coming down to the top of the Mountain and going up again. Gn XXVIII:17 must have been interpreted as meaning that this here on the Meadow is the House of God and that on the Mountain is the Gate of Heaven. The current Samaritan tradition sets Luzah on the top of the Mountain and accordingly locates the place of Jacob's vision there. This tradition is assumed in Jubilees XXVII:19 and 25. Those that set Jacob on the Mountain must have taken the verse to mean this here on the Mountain is the House of God and this here, the same place, is the Gate of Heaven. Arguments could be mounted for both interpretations as being the plain meaning of the verse. There is, however, an important additional expectation in the words quoted by A.F. here. The top of the Mountain must have been regarded by the Dositheans as the location of the Garden or the way to the Garden just above. This is in fact the known Samaritan tradition. It follows that the four rivers that flow out from the Garden even now in the Time of Fānūta must flow from under the Mountain at some level of existence. This too is the known Samaritan tradition. It would follow that the Land of Zawīlah or חיילה Abbīlā in Gn II:11, outside the Garden, is the Meadow. (But note the warning against misreading the halachic question of whether or not being on ground on the bottom slope of the Mountain is equivalent to being on the top of the Mountain for certain purposes, confusing this question with remnants of Dositheanism. See my *Use, Authority, and Exegesis etc.*, note 121). The next question is then whether they were just making an analogy, or really were waiting for the manifestation of the occulted Garden. Did they manage to reconcile the two expectations? I think yes, but this is for another study.

82:14. The form printed here is the original, but there are explanatory expansions in the mss. Vilmar's apparatus is not quite right. Here is the distribution. As printed SBCDL₂L₃Y; حساب الحق الذي JL₁M₁P₁H; حساب الحق الذي A; بايدينا من سيدنا فنحس حساب الحق الذي Khadr. The explanation by Khadr that they copied the Jews (the Rabbinic Jews) because they had no knowledge of the calculation of the calendar is hasty and not thought out. They must have had access to this knowledge from Dositheus onwards.

82:15. Khadr has correctly understood the situation and the implications of what is reported here and elsewhere. He correctly paraphrases "they modified the Festivals and the Passover sacrifice". The dahīyah (a singular noun, not a plural) is what in English is loosely called the Passover sacrifice, in the second half of the afternoon of the fourteenth day

of the first month **outside** the Tabernacle, which is **not of the same category as the sacrifices of the Tabernacle**. The reason they didn't perform the Passover sacrifice (for want of a better word) on the afternoon of the 14th and eat it on the Passover, the 15th, after sunset, was that this ceremony had to be performed outside the Sanctuary, and if there is no Sanctuary, there is no outside. They would have had a special synagogue service. There is a mistaken and meaningless reading الاعياد الضحية in CD, the remnant of the correct reading in a smudged exemplar. The scribe of S has started to write الضحية and then crossed it out and written الصيحة which is copied by B. The reading printed by Vilmar is no more than a wrong guess by the scribe of S, though Vilmar had no way of knowing this. Group 1(c) has the same as S¹B. Ms. A has the correct reading, and so has all of Group 2. Here we see a certain instance of the narrow base of SBCD, the difficulty in reading their ancestral exemplar and specifically the signs of **partial** obliteration of a word. We also have a certain instance of the ancestry of Group 2 and A being from a ms. or mss. that were undamaged, and the preservation of the original reading in spite of the secondary recensional activity behind Group 2 and A.

82:15-16. It says "commandment" فريضه that is, one commandment, and the word is connected to both "fasting" and "Priestly share". These are the two sides of a single commandment. The Israelites are to bring the tērūma to the Priests. The Priests (and their families) are to eat it in a state of holiness קדש qādeš [Rabbinic קדושה]. This is a grade higher than cleanness טהרה ṭarra. The fasting is part of the preparation for entry into holiness. It does not mean not eating. It means refraining from sexual activity for the requisite period, so that the tērūma can be eaten on the third day. It could be guessed that there is the assumption of not eating any food that is not holy within six hours before eating the tērūma. One also assumes that the term صيام implicitly includes prayer and devotional reading, like its implication in Islam. I don't know what the Hebrew word behind the Arabic term would be at the time of writing this article. I don't know of any disagreement between Samaritans, Karaites, and Rabbanites on the requirements for entering the state of holiness. The word in the text here is الصيام "the fasting" not الصوم "the Fast", so there is no connection with the Day of Atonement. The use of this Arabic term to mean refraining from sex (along with not eating for a certain period) is normal and common in Islam and one wonders why this has not been noticed in comments on this passage. There is a vestige of this practice of the Priestly share in the Jewish practice of not eating the right foreleg of an animal slaughtered. It is not given to the Priests either, in agreement with the Dosithean reasoning. The tērūma can be given to Priests anywhere. The Dositheans must have said that it did depend on the existence of the Sanctuary even if not brought to it. Some of the scribes of the mss. have missed all this entirely. The correct reading is in SBCD (D has. والنصب) Ms. L₂ has omitted the words. L₃Y have changed والعرش والنصيب to والعرش, showing that the scribe thought the Dositheans had dropped both the Day of Atonement and Booths. Mss. JN₁ with the Hebrew translation have rewritten the wording, giving one wrong set of words saying they didn't fast on the day of Atonement, and one right saying they didn't give their share to the Priests and correctly using the term رفع, which renders tērūma: وايتلوا يصومو يوم هكفور وايتلوا رفع ذبايحهم الى بني لوى Mss. M₁L₁ have the same double gloss in much the same words. Ms. A is the same and a text of this type could have

been the source of M₁ here. Khaḏr follows the reading of A but expands it.

82:16-83:1. By observing Pentecost on the wrong day they made themselves noticeable in public. A.F. (or perhaps his source) makes a logical connection here, by writing: “They counted the fifty days as the Jews do, and made their offensiveness public”. The Dositheans agreed with the practice of the Pharisees, and thus the standard Rabbinic practice that followed. Other Samaritans (i.e. not the Dositheans) agreed and agree with the Boethusians (probably the Sadducees) and the Karaites. Contrary to the common assumption of a two-way division, the matter is not nearly so simple. Four separate incompatible practices are attested. For a detailed discussion, see my *Principles of Samaritan Halachah* on Lv XXIII:15.

83:1. Although some mss. have *لكاهنتهم* as printed by Vilmar, the ms. evidence for a different reading is much stronger. Here are the readings: *כל תועבותם* Hebrew translation from *كل كرهيتهم* in the Arabic; *جميع الكرايه* Khaḏr from the same reading behind the Hebrew translation; *لكرهيتهم* all of Group 2 and A; corruption of this reading as *لكرتيتهم* in S, the origin of the false reading in CD followed by L₂L₃Y; *لكرهتهم* B, a deliberate departure from its exemplar S and a deliberate correction; *لكاهنتهم* CD; *الى كاهنتهم* L₂L₃Y. It is clear that the reading of SB and Group 2 is the original, being supported by both families and being the harder reading within its family. The quote by Khaḏr and the Hebrew translation show the explanation of the anomalous letter *lâm* as being due to partial obliteration of *كل*. The meaning of the verb is not “allowed” but “made public”.

83:1. No ms. has both *لكاهنتهم* and then *ان* as printed by Vilmar. This word *ان* if it is present follows *لكرهيتهم* showing that this word *ان* must be the remnant of something else. The word *ان* is in all mss. of Group 2 and A. The Hebrew translation renders the Arabic *وكانوا* which is supported by Khaḏr, who has *وكانوا (اذا دخلوا)*. The *نو* has been read as a final *nûn*. This section of text is a good example of a damaged exemplar lying behind all the extant complete mss. except the ms. used by Khaḏr and used for the Hebrew translation soon afterwards. See also 83:14.

83:1-3. The term *ناظر* or *ناظر* is a standard Samaritan technical term. See the index of technical terms in my *Principles*. See ch. XIII of *Al-Kitâb al-Kâfi* for a definition and more detail. It means in a state of uncleanness that can communicate seven days’ uncleanness to a person or artefact coming into contact with it. The Arabic form *nâṭir* is the Aramaic passive participle *נָטַר* *nâṭer* adapted slightly. The passive sense is lost in the Arabic form. The occasional spelling in Hebrew letters shows it was felt to be borrowed. The form *ناظر* is fully Arabic. In Syria-Palestine it would be pronounced *ناصر*. The mss. fluctuate. SCDL₂L₃Y have *ناظر* in both instances here. M₁N₁P₁ have *ناظر* in both instances. AJ have *ناظر* then *ناظر*. In the History by Khaḏr the forms fluctuate without any pattern. In the *Kâfi*, ch. XIII, line 11 in my edition, both are well attested. The *Kâfi* explains this word as meaning sequestration, and treats it as an abstract noun when defining it. Khaḏr treats it syntactically as a noun in the first instance here, and either as a noun or an adjective in the second instance. The same applies to Group 2 of the mss. and A. The first group treat it as an adjective in both cases. Vilmar has followed Group 1 and prints *البيت الناظر* in both instances. All occurrences in ch. XIII of the *Kâfi* are as abstract nouns or could be taken that way. I have never seen it declined as an adjective. The Arabic *waḏiḥ* translates the

Hebrew *צָרוּעַ* *ṣāru*. The form *واضح* printed by Silvestre de Sacy without comment is not in the mss. used by him, though it does exist, and J has it here. B has *واضح*. There is nothing distinctively Dosithean in either the opinion or the argument mentioned here. As all sects would have agreed with the Dositheans, and as leprosy of houses never happened in historical time, the argument used in the case cited must have been used to establish the validity of a principle of argument similar to the Rabbinic *היקש*. See the next note.

83:3-5. Vilmar omits the first instance of *طاهر* “clean” following C, without telling the reader that the reading is unique to this ms. The words “If there was a clean house and they wanted to know whether it was clean or unclean” are correct. Readings attested only by C which are explicable as smoothing out without full understanding are to be rejected. This is one place where A.F. has summarised a difficult source without going back over the resulting words and revising them. Group 1 have *متصل*. Group 2 with A have *ومتصل*. The inferior sub-group CDL₂L₃Y have “someone would sit”. What is described here is not a real practice, since leprosy of houses never happened. It is the proposed solution to a difficulty in argument, using the case to assert the validity of the principle. The wording is condensed but the argument is perfectly clear if the principles of halachic argument are known. Khaḏr gives a useful expansion that puts the meaning beyond doubt. The question here is a situation of what in Rabbinic terms would be called *חשש* “reasonable assumption” which is more than *ספק* “doubt”. (In *Principles of Samaritan Halachah* I translated the Arabic equivalent *شبهه* as “plausibility”). Normally a house could never be in a doubtful state because it can’t be unclean till the Priest declares it unclean, signs or not. On the other hand, the sign might disappear before the Priest arrived. In that case the house would be clean, because the Priest could not pronounce it unclean, though those that were scrupulous might treat it as if it were unclean for seven days. But what if no inspection of the second house had been done before the Priest arrived? It would not be known whether there had ever been any signs. This sets up an insoluble problem. The question is not whether the second house is unclean, but whether it ought or ought not to be treated as doubtfully but plausibly unclean. On one hand, the presumption in the case of a doubt about a doubt (Rabbinic *ספק דספק*) is logically that the house is to be treated as clean. On the other hand, there is a positive presumption (Rabbinic *חשש*) from the house next door that it ought to be treated as if unclean, even if strictly not unclean. Insoluble. *תיקן*. The Dositheans did what the Talmud does: make an arbitrary decision. They differed from the Talmud by taking the decision out of human hands. But what really is the question here? Leprosy of houses never actually occurred within historical time. So the question must be about authority. We don’t know what this was precisely, but here is a guess. If the final arbitrary decision is taken out of human hands, then the implication is that no secular decision by a committee can have final authority in any question at all. Indirectly but effectively the ultimate authority of the High Priest for decisions is asserted and strengthened.

83:5-7. The usual explanation, that the Dositheans wanted to avoid the temptation of immersing something on the Sabbath, shows ignorance of the halachah. Even if immersed on the Sabbath, the utensil would not be clean till sunset. (The Rabbanite halachah goes its own way on this). Aside from this, immersion is not a casual act. You have to

walk to a suitable body of water. Carrying the vessel outside the house on the Sabbath would not be permissible. Besides, the Dositheans would not have needed any artificial devices to restrain them. The real explanation can be seen by observing the practice of some people now, who immerse their vessels before the Sabbath so they can be absolutely certain they are clean on the Sabbath. For this purpose, the vessels can be anything except pottery.

83:10. Vilmar follows CD. Khaḍr has understood correctly. The spelling *من سوي* for *من سوا* = Classical *من سواء* in CD is unexpected, and might be a mistake for *من سوا*. The spelling *من سو* in SB with Group 2 and A is a mistake for *من سوا* with the alif having dropped out because of the alif at the start of the next word. The usage itself is normal for Arabic of this period. I think it is still normal Syrian-Palestinian usage. There is no doubt that the pronunciation intended is [min sawa]. After some thought, I have kept the spelling of CD instead of *من سوا* which would have been the original spelling. The Hebrew translation is right off track this time.

83:11-12. On the term Rabbîs and the function of those few with this title, see my *Use, Authority and Exegesis etc.*, p. 618 and note 91. (Rabbîs is the correct form. The plural is Rabâbisah). A.F. has difficulty expressing himself here, as I have had difficulty translating. Dositheus became the Imâm of what is here anachronistically called the Dositheans. From the point of view of the Dositheans he was High Priest; from the point of view of the opposition he was Rabbîs of the Dositheans. See the passage from A.F. on the Rabbîs of the Sebuæans, quoted in full in the chapter just mentioned. (The Sebuæans are probably the Dositheans, but that is for a future article). Intercourse with someone not of the right category would have disqualified him from officiating as a Priest. [Note that *خاطبه* is an unusual word carefully chosen by A.F. to render the Hebrew *זונה* which as a halachic term does not mean prostitute. The verb applies to both sexes]. Only D has the order of words printed by Vilmar. Unique readings of D are nearly always inferior. Aside from this, the logical order must be that Dositheus was first disqualified and then removed from his position. As son of the High Priest he could never lose his position of deputy Rabbîs as long as he was able to officiate as a Priest. We have another version of this tradition. In the second account of the Dositheans, the narrative starts with an attempt by Dositheus to frame a prominent Priest called Yēdo on precisely the same charge so that he would be unable to officiate as deputy Rabbîs with the High Priest on the Day of Atonement. [On the name Yēdo, see at 83:14]. At this point the reader has not yet been told that Dositheus is the son of the High Priest. A.F. has used a document in which incompatible sources, some probably accurate, some made up, have been combined to make a scurrilous fiction. One wonders whether Yēdo, that is, Yēdāya, “God knows” is a symbolic name that originally belonged to Dositheus as the second Moses. See Dt XXXIV:10 with Nu XII:6-8. As Paul says, we will know because we are known. In the second account, Yēdo is said to be the most pious and learned person of his time. In the first account, Dositheus is said to be the most learned person of his time. In the second account, Yēdo is innocent and the accusation fraudulent. In the first account, Dositheus is guilty on evidence duly verified. In both accounts Dositheus is the son of the High Priest.

83:13. On the name and title, see on 83:15. The name is probably a diminutive of *אלעזר* *Ēlāzār* like the name *עזרא*. Ezra to the Samaritans is the embodiment of heresy. This re-

semblance of the names might be significant in the development of the legendary material about Dositheus. Khaḍr (or his source) takes the first occurrence of the name to be a name of opprobrium bestowed by his opponents playing on the sound. Thus he has two forms, first *זרה* zarra “the foreigner”, then *זרעת* *zār'rēēt*. See on this favourable title my *Use, Authority and Exegesis etc.*

83:14. The reading *هجا* in CDL₃Y instead of *بايجا* can be discarded. It has arisen from an unsuccessful attempt at making sense of a meaningless group of words. The witnesses reduce to C and D probably not independently. CD are not to be trusted when corruption is known to have occurred, first because the scribe of C is not always accurate and second because the scribes of C and D make guesses. This leaves *بايجا* in S, *باجا* in B (a secondary alteration) and *بايجا* in all mss. of the second group and in A. (The Persian letter *پ* [p] marks a point without dots, potentially <t, th, y, n, b>, but usually <y> whenever the omission of dots is deliberate). This last is the right reading. One value of S can be seen here. This ms. often preserves groups of letters from the damaged ancestral exemplar that make no sense as they stand, without any secondary guessing and emendation. There was some damage even to the ancestor of the second group and A, since the words are the same as in S. Here is what Khaḍr has: *فعمل كتابا) يبيح به الاشيا المحرمه وقال ان كل (فعمل كتابا) (He then composed a book) in which he declared permissible all the forbidden things. He said all High Priests other than him were illegitimate”. The Hebrew translation derives from the same Arabic text expanded by Khaḍr, translating *כל מאום חרם* *ינעש ספר וחייב בו כל מאום חרם* *יאמר בו כל הכהנים אשר אינם ממנו אינם קשיטים*. This interpretation by the learned High Priest Ya'qūb bin Hārūn is correct. Dositheus said that any future High Priest not descended from him would be illegitimate. Here is the origin of the alternative chronology of High Priests that forced Abu 'l-Fath into putting his second notice of Dositheus (as well as Jesus, Simon Magus, and Philo Iudaeus) after the Council of Nicaea! He must have known what he was doing, and decided to re-start his narrative going back a few centuries. If the second account and the following account of Jesus and the following third account of the Dosithean sub-sects were put right after the first account, the sequence would work. The difficulty with doing that would have been that the first account is incompatible with the long fanciful story about Dositheus and Yēdo *יהדו* at the start of the second account. This name Yēdo is a diminutive of *ידעיה* *yē'dāya* like the Masoretic *עדו* and *ידוע*. [The letter *ה* is a vowel-letter, and not etymological]. This Yaddua is the last High Priest of the Jewish line before the Persian period and the last mentioned in Chronicles-Ezra-Nehemiah, and therefore the last High Priest of the era of the Jewish prophets. This Yēdo was next in line for the High Priesthood after Iqbon, whose unstable behaviour would have made his tenure uncertain. Anyway, Yēdo would have succeeded him naturally. This means Yēdo could have been the last Samaritan High Priest of the Persian period and the from the Dosithean viewpoint the last High Priest before Dositheus at the very start of Hellenistic rule, after which only those descended from Dositheus would have been regarded by them as legitimate. This would explain the significance of Dositheus questioning the eating of by Yēdo of one category of *תרומה* *tērūma*, reported by A.F. in the second account at 152:4-9. Yēdo represents the opposing side at the time of the Dosithean separation or perhaps the innovating side if it was the Dositheans that*

were the traditionalists. What Dositheus queries is the eating of the meat of a first-born animal by Yēdo in the state of holiness required for the eating of sacrificial offerings, when the blood has not been sprinkled on the altar; which could obviously not be done because there was no Sanctuary and no altar. Yēdo replies with the reasonable analogy of the eating of bread. Lv XXIII:14 says no bread is to be eaten after Passover before the wave-offering in the Sanctuary, but it is known that bread can be eaten these days even though there is no Sanctuary. The debate on this question has survived the legendary embellishment. We know from Abu 'l-Faḥ 82:15-16 that the Dositheans did not accept this solution. A.F. knew Dositheus was connected with a High Priest Iqbon עִקְבֹן and in the account of the persecutions under Decius and later there was a High Priest Iqbon. Perhaps A.F. knew what he was doing, and had decided not to make his use of a Dosithean document for some of the information about the persecution under Decius too obvious. This observation will help sort out the chronology of both Mārḳe and Baba Rabba as well. But back to the text. We have to assume some minimal adjustment on the part of Khaḍr, rather than necessarily accepting this as a word for word quotation, but he has something that makes sense without losing the two difficult words. We could suppose a very old error affecting all the European mss. of every recension. Jamgotchian has found indisputably original readings in the St. Petersburg fragments where there is a really serious error in all extant complete mss. of all textforms. The form بايحا is certain. If Khaḍr changed the stem from Stem I (fa'al) to Stem IV (af'al), then he was dissatisfied with the meaning "revealing". If he was dissatisfied with the meaning of this word, then he did not understand the meaning of the whole group of words. As the stem حرم must have been before him, judging from his quotation, then he must have taken that stem in the wrong meaning as well, thinking of the meaning "being forbidden" rather than the meaning "being sacrosanct". So that gives the following words, which made no sense to him. "(He then composed a book) revealing the things sacred. In it he declared illegitimate (or excommunicating) all the High Priests" (فعل كتابا) بايحا الحريم احرم فيه. "(He then composed a book) permitting the things forbidden". and made what would have seemed a minor emendation, moving the verb from Stem I to Stem IV. This reconstruction is simple and neat and plausible. If it is not accepted, then here is the honest translation of what is in the mss.: "(He composed a book) revealing all the High Priests".

83:14. The form فانه printed by Vilmar from CD is correct, but not necessarily best. The scribes of Group 2 and A and the ms. used by Khaḍr and for the Hebrew translation have misunderstood the intention or found it too surprising, and have بان making "he innovated that no-one was more learned than him", with an impossible use of the verb. SB have فان instead of فانه, taking what follows as a noun clause. This is probably more original than the reading of CD printed by Vilmar.

83:15. Here is the distribution of readings: ولذلك اسمه SBJH₁; ولذلك اسمه D; وكذلك اسمه CL₂L₃Y; وكذلك اسمه AM₁N₁P₁L₁. The Hebrew translation renders the Arabic as זרה וזהו שמו זרה but in H₁ the name is corrected to זרעה with a letter added above the line. (At the time of writing I don't know the reading of H₂). The quote by Khaḍr is وكان اصل زرعته "which was the meaning behind his name זרעה זר'רēt". Khaḍr has understood correctly. The mss. of his

book fluctuate between זרה zarra "the stranger" and זרע for the first occurrence of the name, but as his son Nāji bin Khaḍr writes זרה this can be taken to be the author's intention. Khaḍr differs from all the extant mss. in not having the form زرعہ zārāa in either place. The form of name cited by him in the first occurrence is secondary, since it is easier to go from זרעה to זרה than the other way. It is uncertain whether Khaḍr made the change himself or whether it was like that in his ms., but as he always tries to keep the data of his source, the second is more likely. On the other hand, the form זרעה זר'rēt in the second instance is original, and Khaḍr draws attention to it on purpose. On the significance of this favourable title see my *Use, Authority and Exegesis etc.* It has a connection, not fully understood, with the new reading in the Dosithean text of the Torah, the word צאתר ṣāātar instead of צוזב izzob in Exodus XII:22, recorded by A.F. at 155:14-17. If this reconstruction of the name is not accepted, then the reading is زرعہ as printed by Vilmar.

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7. Transcription Conventions

Samaritan Hebrew and Aramaic are transcribed according to the standard system established by Ze'ev Ben-Ḥayyim. For the sake of clarity for non-specialists, the system has been modified in two ways. A double-long two-peaked vowel is transcribed as <ūū> and so on rather than as <ū:> and so on. A vowel between [ε] and [ə] in a final unstressed closed syllable is transcribed as <e> rather than <ə>. Note that the sound [ʕ] ε does exist in these two dialects, though only before a and ā, and is transcribed as <ʕ>. Stress is penultimate, except that double-peaked vowels always have the main stress regardless of position.

Melbourne, March 2008